

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 3-ETHYL-3,4-DIHYDROISOCOUMARINS (2)*

Compd. no.	Yield %	B.p. (10 mm) °C	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}^{**}$ cm^{-1}	δ
2a	22	160	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 715 (δ -lactone)	1.09 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.84 (2H, complex, CH_2OH), 2.6 and 3.2 (2H, dd, J 11, 17 Hz and 4, 17 Hz), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.38 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 7.1 (1H, dd, J 1, 8 Hz, H_6), 7.3 (1H, t, J 8 Hz, H_7) and 7.7 (1H, dd, J 1, 8 Hz, H_6)
2b	29	72 ^a	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 720 (δ -lactone)	1.06 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_3), 2.9 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, benzylic CH_2), 3.84 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.4 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 6.8 (2H, complex, H_6 and H_7) and 8.05 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_6)
2c	13	140	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 730 (δ -lactone)	1.05 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_3), 2.85 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, benzylic CH_2), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.2 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$) and 6.7–7.4 (3H, complex, H_6 , H_6 and H_7)
2d	19	130	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 730 (δ -lactone)	1.08 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_3), 2.34 (3H, s, aromatic CH_3), 2.85 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, benzylic CH_2), 4.39 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 7.1 (2H, complex ortho-coupled H_6 and H_6 protons signals merged) and 7.75 (1H, s ^b , H_6)
2e	17	155	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 725 (δ -lactone)	1.01 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_3), 2.35 (3H, s, aromatic CH_3), 2.85 (2H, d, benzylic CH_2), 4.35 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 7.0 (1H, s ^b , H_6), 7.1 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_7), 7.9 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_6)
2f	23	74 ^a	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$	1 720 (δ -lactone)	1.1 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 1.8 (2H, complex, CH_2CH_3), 2.7 and 3.1 (2H, dd, J 11, 17 Hz and 4, 17 Hz), 3.8 and 3.9 (each 3H, s, OCH_3 at C-5 and C-6), 4.3 (1H, complex, $\text{ArCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{O})\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 6.9 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_7) and 7.8 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H_6)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

**Compounds 2a, 2b and 2f taken in nujol and 2c, 2d and 2f neat. ^aM.p. (°C). ^bSignals not resolved into a meta-coupled doublets.

dry ether under N_2 -atmosphere during 10 min. The resulting red metalation mixture was refluxed for 45 min, cooled to 0 to -5° and to it 1,2-butylene oxide (9.0 ml) in dry ether was added during 5 min. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0° for 2 h and further 2 h at room temperature. The alkaline hydrolysis workup^o of the reaction mixture gave the 3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarin derivatives. Thus 5-methoxy-, 6-methoxy-, 8-methoxy-, 7-methyl-, 6-methyl- and 5,6-dimethoxy-3-ethyl-3,4-dihydroisocoumarins were synthesised (2a–f, Table 1).

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Studies on Flavonoids. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 7-n-Butoxy-6-nitro/H-flavones, -flavonols and -flavanones

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FLAVONOIDS have been found to be associated with diverse biological activities¹. The present work reports the preparation of 7-n-butoxy-6-nitro-flavones, -flavonols and -flavanones and 7-n-butoxy-flavones, -flavonols and -flavanones of types 2, 3 and 4 respectively. These are derived from previously synthesised² 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones and 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxychalcones (1) which have been prepared from 2-hydroxy-4-n-

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NOTES

butoxy-5-nitroacetophenone or 2-hydroxy-4-n-butoxyacetophenone and various araldehydes, and their biological activity² evaluated.

The chalcones (1) on oxidation with selenium dioxide in amyl alcohol³ were smoothly converted into the flavones (2). The chalcones (1) when subjected to Algar-Flynn-Oyamada oxidation⁴ using alkaline hydrogen peroxide gave the flavonols (3). Cyclisation⁵ of the chalcones (1) in ethanolic medium and in presence of sulphuric acid (10%) yielded the corresponding flavanones (4) (Scheme 1).

X = NO₂/H, R = Aryl
Scheme 1

The structures of the compounds have been supported by elemental analysis and ir and pmr spectral data. The compounds have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

The flavones gave characteristic ir bands at 1 620–1 640 (C=O), 1 550 (C=C), and 1 100–1 255 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); the flavonols at 3 257–3 367 (OH), 1 605–1 610 (C=O), 1 560 (C=C) and 1 085 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C) and the flavanones at 1 685–1 700 (C=O) and 1 065–1 180 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C). The flavones showed the following characteristic pmr signals at δ 4.3 (9H, m, 7-OC₄H₉), 6.64 (1H, s, 3-H), 6.47 (1H, s, 5-H) and 7.0–7.7 (5H, m, ArH).

The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup-diffusion⁶ method against gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*. Some of the compounds containing halogen like bromine and chlorine atom introduced in aryl part of the flavonoid molecule showed moderate activity (15–22 mm zone of inhibition) against *S. aureus*. Almost all the compounds were found to be resistant against *E. coli*. Most of the compounds were found moderately active (15–22 mm) against *A. niger*.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	X	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	Phenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	115	65
2b	2'-Bromophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ NBr	170	63
2c	4'-Chlorophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	95	52
2d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl ₂	155	55
2e	2'-Methoxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	85	52
2f	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	220	62
2g	4'-Methylphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	85	45
2h	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	210	65
2i	4'-N-Dimethylaminophenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂	115	62
2j	4'-Bromophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ Br	100	68
2k	2'-Chlorophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl	90	52
2l	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₂	175	46
3a	Phenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	135	80
3b	2'-Bromophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ NBr	118	70
3c	4'-Chlorophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ NCl	180	60
3d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₂ NCl ₂	170–72	55
3e	2'-Methoxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	146	75
3f	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	115	50
3g	4'-Methylphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₂	140	55
3h	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	215	75
3i	4'-N-Dimethylaminophenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂	182	58
3j	4'-Bromophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ Br	220	78
3k	2'-Chlorophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl	140–02	65
3l	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₂	140	52
4a	Phenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	118	80
4b	2'-Bromophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ NBr	165	80
4c	4'-Chlorophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ NCl	191–02	82
4d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ NCl ₂	240	70
4e	2'-Methoxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₂ N	190	60
4f	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	140	65
4g	4'-Methylphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₂ N	172	80
4h	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	142	75
4i	4'-N-Dimethylaminophenyl	NO ₂	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₂ N ₂	75	50
4j	4'-Bromophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ Br	50	50
4k	2'-Chlorophenyl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ Cl	50–2	45
4l	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₂	183	50

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CDCl_3) taken using TMS as internal standard.

7-n-Butoxy-6-nitroflavone (2a): A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcone (1; 1 g) and SeO_2 (1 g) in dry n-amyl alcohol (15–20 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath at 130–40° for 24 h. The precipitated selenium was filtered off and the filtrate steam-distilled to remove n-amyl alcohol. The residual brownish solid was crystallised from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 115° (Found: C, 67.32; H, 5.20; N, 3.9. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6\text{N}$ calcd. for: C, 67.25; H, 5.01; N, 4.13%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 630 (C=O), 1 550 (C=C) and 1 150 cm^{-1} (C–O–C).

Similarly, other substituted flavones were prepared (2b–1; Table 1).

7-n-Butoxy-6-nitroflavonol (3a): It was prepared by the reported method⁴, (80%), m.p. 135° (Found: C, 64.16; H, 4.86; N, 4.0. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_6\text{N}$ calcd. for: C, 64.22; H, 4.78; N, 3.94%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (OH), 1 605 (C=O), 1 560 (C=C) and 1 085 cm^{-1} (C–O–C).

Similarly, other flavonols were prepared (3b–1; Table 1).

7-n-Butoxy-6-nitroflavanone (4a): It was prepared by the reported method⁵, (80%), m.p. 118° (Found: C, 66.92; H, 5.51; N, 3.9. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ calcd. for: C, 66.86; H, 5.57; N, 4.10%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 690 (C=O) and 1 100 cm^{-1} (C–O–C).

Similarly, other flavanones were prepared (4b–1; Table 1).

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Preparation of 5-Methyl-N-propylamino-2,3-dihydroindole Derivatives

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INDOLINES exhibit various biological activities¹ and act as dye². Here, we report the preparation of some of indoline derivatives. *p*-Toluidine was reacted with acrylonitrile to give 2, which when condensed with chloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine in benzene followed by reaction with AlCl_3 formed *N*-cyanoethyl-5-methyl-2-oxoindole (3). Compound 3 when reduced with LiAlH_4 in THF afforded 4. The reduction of $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ to NH_2 was indicated by the disappearance of ir band at 2 250 cm^{-1} and appearance of a band at 3 200–3 000 cm^{-1} . Various derivatives of 4 were prepared.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 90 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a EI-MS instrument. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

N-Cyanoethyl-p-toluidine (2): *p*-Toluidine (53.5 g, 0.5 mol) and acrylonitrile (26.5 g, 0.5 mol) in acetic acid (2.5 ml) were refluxed for about 15 h and then distilled under reduced pressure. The residue was crystallised with CHCl_3 which on evaporation gave a solid which crystallised from ethanol to yield 2 (36.5 g, 50%), m.p. 102° (Found: C, 82.15; H, 8.13; N, 9.50. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2$ requires: C, 82.19; H, 8.21; N, 9.58%); λ_{max} (ethanol) 265 and 300 nm; ν_{max} (nujol) 3 250 (NH), 2 250 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (Ph); δ (CCl_4) 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 2.8 (2H, t, CH_2CN), 3.65 (2H, t, NCH_2), 4.1 (1H, s, NH) and 7.1 (4H, s, ArH).

N-Cyanoethyl-5-methyl-2-oxoindole (3): A mixture of 2 (40 g, 0.5 mol) and chloroacetyl chloride (24 g, 0.5 mol) in benzene (40 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 h in the presence of triethyl-